

India-ASEAN Cooperation in the Indo-Pacific: Building an Inclusive and Rules-Based Regional Order

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ABSTRACT: Oceans, covering nearly 70 percent of the Earth's surface and facilitating around 90 percent of the global trade, remain central to contemporary geopolitics. In the 21st century, the Indo-Pacific, comprising the Indian and the Pacific Oceans, emerged as the principal geopolitical and geoeconomic theatre in international relations. The region's strategic significance is heightened by the presence of critical sea lanes of communication (SLOCs) and strategic chokepoints, positioning it as the epicentre of great power competition. Simultaneously, it faces a complex array of traditional and non-traditional maritime security challenges, necessitating cooperative and rule-based approaches to regional order. Within this context, India and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) occupy pivotal positions due to their geographical centrality and strategic interdependence. This paper examines the evolving contours of India-ASEAN cooperation in the Indo-Pacific, which focuses on four key domains: socio-cultural engagement, economic integration, connectivity initiatives, and maritime security collaboration. It argues that a deepened India-ASEAN partnership is essential for fostering regional stability, enhancing resilience, and sustaining an inclusive and rule-based order.

KEYWORDS: Indo-Pacific, India, ASEAN, maritime security, geopolitics, rule-based regional order

1. INTRODUCTION

The Indo-Pacific region, stretching from the eastern shores of Africa to the western Pacific, has become a geopolitical hotspot in the 21st century. With a huge geographical area and abundant resources, the region has become a point of contention among nations, also leading to great power politics and competition among major powers like the United States (U.S.) and China. China's resorting to illegal expansionism in the form of claiming islands in the South China Sea (SCS) and negating the decision of the Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA) in the 2016 Philippines v. China case has necessitated major stakeholders in the region to come together to establish a rules-based order. The growing emergence of non-traditional security issues, like maritime piracy, maritime terrorism, climate change, narcotics and arms smuggling, among others, hampers a just order in the region. The region is also an economic hotbed, with 50 percent of global trade and 40 percent of global oil passing through the region (Vice President's Secretariat, 2023). Any disruption in the SLOCs due to maritime security threats directly poses a challenge to the free flow of goods among Indo-Pacific nations. The region, thus, requires enhanced cooperation and coordination among nations to challenge these shared security challenges.

India and ASEAN are among the most important stakeholders in the Indo-Pacific, with the potential to reshape the regional order towards a secure environment. The relationship between India and ASEAN is not new, as they have shared deep cultural and religious bonds for centuries. Various religious and historical texts that are part of the archival collection of the Ministry of Culture point towards such references. Maritime trade relations were one key aspect that connected these regions. The trade was not only the trade of goods but also culture, language, architecture, and religion. Buddhism, a religion that took root in India, had a huge influence on Southeast Asian nations and is prevalent even today. Angkor Wat in Cambodia is the world's largest religious structure, dedicated to the Hindu-Buddhist religion (Ministry of Culture, 2025).

In contemporary times, India and ASEAN share stable economic, political, diplomatic, and cultural ties with each other. The Indian Ocean and the Pacific Ocean form an integral part of both India and ASEAN, and they aspire to keep the region safe and secure. Against this backdrop, India and ASEAN intend to advance cooperation and nurture a free and open Indo-Pacific. India and ASEAN envisioned their Indo-Pacific visions in the form of the Indo-Pacific Ocean Initiative (IPOI) and the ASEAN Outlook on the Indo-Pacific (AOIP) in 2019, both overlapping on the pillars of maritime cooperation, connectivity, sustainable development, and economic cooperation, thus strengthening their convergence in the region. They have stable economic relations and joint ventures on trade, connectivity, and infrastructure, and both are working on many security frameworks to establish peace and

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harmony in the region. At the 22nd ASEAN-India Summit held in Kuala Lumpur on 26 October 2025, Prime Minister (PM) Modi, in his opening remarks, pointed out that “the 21st century is our century, the century of India and ASEAN” (PMIndia, 2025). He expressed confidence that the ASEAN Community Vision 2045 and the goal of Viksit Bharat 2047 will build a bright future for all in the Indo-Pacific region (ASEAN Main Portal, 2025).

The paper builds on the theoretical frameworks of liberal institutionalism and constructivism, highlighting the relevance attributed to international institutions as well as norms, culture, and traditions in the Indo-Pacific domain. Contextualising the India-ASEAN relations and cooperation in the Indo-Pacific, which serves as a common area of interest, the paper defines their respective Indo-Pacific visions and India’s strong support to ASEAN’s centrality. Both India and the bloc converge on socio-cultural aspects, where they collaborate on education, health, and people-to-people exchanges in order to foster cultural assimilation as well as work towards common goals. Because of the physical proximity between India and ASEAN, combined with other factors like cultural and maritime linkages, they are a part of a number of joint ventures and initiatives, serving mutual benefits. Economic relations and connectivity projects also form an integral part of India and ASEAN, as evidenced by the peaking trade in goods and services, with the total bilateral trade at USD 120 billion. They are part of various connectivity projects like the India–Myanmar–Thailand (IMT) Trilateral Highway, Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project, and Sabang (Aceh) port cooperation, among others. Such connectivity projects synergise the bilateral relations as well as enhance the economy of the nations associated with them. India and ASEAN share commonality in adhering to the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) for a free, fair, and inclusive Indo-Pacific and are part of various institutional frameworks like the Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA) and the Indian Ocean Naval Symposium (IONS) to work towards this goal.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

India and ASEAN are traditional partners, with historical and cultural linkages dating back centuries. Their convergence in the economic, connectivity, cultural, political, security and defence domains, as well as their geographical proximity, makes them natural allies and partners. The convergence between India and ASEAN can be understood through the lenses of liberal institutionalist and constructivist theories of international relations.

Global and regional institutions in international relations strengthen interdependence, reduce transaction costs and uncertainty and enhance cooperation to combat shared challenges under an anarchical system. It fosters confidence-building measures (CBMs) and collective action, traits that are essential in sensitive zones such as the Indo-Pacific. The rising maritime threats in the region led to the institutionalisation of the Indo-Pacific, leading to the formation of several bodies and frameworks to foster a free, fair, inclusive and rules-based regional order. Regional Cooperation Agreement on Combating Piracy and Armed Robbery against Ships in Asia (ReCAAP), IORA, East Asia Summit, and ASEAN Defence Ministers’ Meeting Plus (ADMM-Plus) are some of the converging frameworks of India and ASEAN aimed at fostering cooperation and enhancing relations in multiple domains. This convergence in institutions and frameworks embodies the institutional logic and the necessity for institutionalism in order to build a harmonious region and reap mutual benefits from each other for growth and development (Devitt, 2011).

India-ASEAN relations can be contextualised through a constructivist lens as well (Theys, 2018). They share a common history, culture, traditions, and maritime exchanges, which are rooted in their links for centuries. They envision an Indo-Pacific that is free and fair, based on the norms of inclusivity and sustainability as well as mutual trust. Both India and ASEAN advocate for the UNCLOS, which is an international treaty establishing legal frameworks in the maritime domain. UNCLOS’s ultimate aim is to establish a maritime global order that abides by the peaceful use and management of ocean resources. UNCLOS is also referred to as the “constitution of the ocean”. The strong advocacy of UNCLOS to be a norm-shaper and establish a rules-based order in the Indo-Pacific is strongly rooted in India and ASEAN. India’s IPOI and ASEAN’s AOIP also find convergence to establish a regional order based on norms and reinforce a normative community.

3. ASEAN CENTRALITY AND INDIA’S INDO-PACIFIC VISION

ASEAN Centrality, as defined by Amitav Acharya, is “a synonym for ASEAN as the leader, driver, architect, institutional hub, vanguard, nucleus or fulcrum of regional cooperation in the wider Asia-Pacific” (Teh, 2022). ASEAN was established in 1967 amid tensions during the Cold War in Southeast Asia. It was formed by five non-communist countries, with the primary aim to foster political stability, economic development and regional solidarity in the volatile geopolitical environment. Over time, it developed into a more institutionalised framework and became a key actor in fostering dialogue and diplomacy, enhancing economic integration, and mediating conflicts in the region and beyond. At present, ASEAN comprises 11 members alongside various dialogue partners, which are channelled through various institutions. ASEAN operationalises through various forums, like the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF), which was established in 1994 to foresee the security dynamics in the region; the ASEAN Defence Ministers’ Meeting Plus (ADMM+), a framework to strengthen security and defence cooperation between ASEAN and its dialogue partners; and the East Asia Summit (EAS), a regional forum comprising ASEAN members and its dialogue partners to strengthen regional cooperation and combat shared challenges.

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Gradually, the institutionalisation of ASEAN was strengthened with the framing of the ASEAN Charter on 15 December 2008 at the ASEAN Secretariat in Jakarta, entailing a legal status to ASEAN. It codifies rules, regulations and norms that need to be followed by member states, and the legally binding agreement makes the charter enforceable (Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation, Kingdom of Cambodia, 2007).

The Indo-Pacific region garnered geopolitical significance in the 21st century, as earlier, the Asia-Pacific construct was eminent (and exists today as well). The emergence of non-traditional security threats, like piracy, maritime terrorism, climate change, human trafficking, narcotics, arms smuggling, migration, and illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing, along with the increasing expansionism of China, were among the few factors that led to the attention of the world's attention towards the Indo-Pacific. The region holds immense strategic importance in the present times, owing to the huge amounts of trade and commerce traversing the region. The region also hosts important SLOCs and maritime chokepoints, which are key for maritime trade and energy security.

Since the inception of the Indo-Pacific construct, India has always kept ASEAN centrality at the heart of its policy documents. Speaking at the Shangri-La conference in 2018, when PM Modi outlined India's Indo-Pacific vision, he clearly articulated the importance of ASEAN centrality in establishing a rules-based order and unimpeded trade and commerce in the region (Durai, 2025). This stance has been strengthened by India's political leaders at international fora, time and again, as exemplified by the remarks of the Minister of External Affairs, S. Jaishankar, at the 1st ASEAN Future Forum in 2024, where he said that

ASEAN is at the heart of our Act East Policy and is a crucial pillar in India's wider Indo-Pacific vision. We support ASEAN unity, centrality and the ASEAN Outlook on the Indo-Pacific. India believes that a strong and unified ASEAN can play a constructive role in the emerging regional architecture of the Indo-Pacific (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2024).

There is also convergence between IPOI and AOIP (see figure 1). Both visions rest on the liberal tenets of international relations and call for inclusivity and adherence to international laws like UNCLOS in combating maritime security challenges. They stress the importance of multilateralism and cooperation in securing a rules-based order in the Indo-Pacific. Dr Prabir De, expert on ASEAN and professor at the Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS), New Delhi, remarked that

There are many complementarities and convergences between India's IPOI and ASEAN's AOIP. This is a nice way to engage countries with common, shared challenges, be it maritime security, maritime safety, maritime ecology, or maritime connectivity. India's interest in the Indo-Pacific is unparalleled. Over 70 percent of our global trade is through the Indo-Pacific economy. There are many common challenges for AOIP and IPOI. AOIP and IPOI talk with each other for collaboration among coast guards, navies, and agencies dealing with maritime alerts, such as tsunami and disaster management (Bhuyan, 2024).

Both IPOI and AOIP were launched in 2019, with the aim of establishing a rules-based order in the Indo-Pacific.

Figure 1: Pillars of IPOI and AOIP and their convergence
Source: Ministry of External Affairs, Indo-Pacific Division Briefs.

As highlighted in Figure 1, IPOI and AOIP overlap on the pillars of maritime cooperation, connectivity, sustainable development, and cooperation, thus strengthening their convergence in the Indo-Pacific. As former ambassador Gurjit Singh argues, both frameworks complement each other, and while IPOI is strategic, i.e., enshrining India's Indo-Pacific vision and operationability,

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AOIP fosters functional inclusivity and gives an idea of the cooperative and developmental character of the Indo-Pacific (Singh, 2022).

4. INDIA-ASEAN CONVERGENCE IN THE INDO-PACIFIC

India and ASEAN's shared vision and goal in the Indo-Pacific lead to their enhanced convergence in various domains, with the ultimate aim of fostering openness, inclusivity, and prosperity in the region. For India, ASEAN lies at the heart of its Indo-Pacific vision and acts as an institutional bridge connecting the Indian and the Pacific Ocean. For ASEAN, India emerges as a nation that fosters inclusivity and not exclusivity, driven by norms, and having the potential to counterbalance the intensified U.S.-China rivalry in the region.

4.1 Socio-Cultural Cooperation

India and ASEAN share deep socio-cultural cooperation, including people-to-people exchanges, cultural assimilation, and cooperation in the areas of education and health. Both India and ASEAN are actively engaged in organising regular activities in the form of ASEAN-India Students Exchange Programmes, Special Course for ASEAN Diplomats, Delhi Dialogue, International Conference on ASEAN-India Cultural and Civilizational Links, ASEAN-India Media Exchange Programme, ASEAN-India Young Farmers Exchange Programme, ASEAN-India Youth Summit and the ASEAN-India Network of Think-Tanks, among others (ASEAN Main Portal, 2023). PM Modi inaugurated the new campus of Nalanda University (which once served as a place of intellectual exchange and learning ground across Asia) at Rajgir, Bihar, on 19 June, 2024. With the campus built on green sustainability, the university is ASEAN-oriented, with courses offered on India-ASEAN historical ties, maritime connectivity, and old writings and texts. It also provides scholarships to the students of the ASEAN student community in order for master's, PhD and PG Diploma programmes to synergise relations and foster bonhomie. India also provides a number of other scholarships as well to ASEAN nations, including the Quad STEM Fellowship, Quad Infrastructure Fellowship, the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR) Scholarships, BIMSTEC Scholarship, Mekong Ganga Cooperation Scholarship Scheme, among others (The ASEAN Magazine, 2024). Educational linkages foster cultural and intellectual exchanges among students, leading to cross-cutting research and collaboration and interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary research. Further, it builds mutual trust and mutual growth, leading to an enhanced and skilled workforce and economic prosperity.

The 24th ASEAN-India Senior Officials' Meeting witnessed the acknowledgement and appreciation given to India for its continued support and contribution of USD 1 million to the COVID-19 ASEAN Response Fund. India and ASEAN have a wide population of 2 billion people, having immense potential to collaborate on global health enhancement and reduce health inequities. The COVID-19 pandemic made the world realise the need for collaboration and cooperation among nations to address shared challenges. India is regarded as the 'pharmacy of the world', and the pandemic witnessed India's proactive role in the manufacture and production of vaccines, and export of PPE kits and other critical care equipment. With India's low cost of production and ASEAN's technological capabilities, they have the potential for mutual collaboration, preparedness and growth in the health domain. India's Ayushman Bharat Health Infrastructure and Digital Health Missions further strengthened India's commitment to public health, capacity building, surveillance, and control. Other than the pandemic, there is also immense scope for collaboration in combating vector-borne diseases (prevalent in both India and Southeast Asia) as well as HIV/AIDS and tuberculosis. ASEAN nations, especially Thailand and Singapore, have the knowledge system and experience of tackling non-communicable diseases (NCDs). ASEAN's improved clinical advances and India's digital health advancement call for mutual collaboration and knowledge sharing for a prosperous regional order (Reddy, 2022).

In line with keeping the spirit of India and ASEAN thriving, India's Commerce Ministry, through Pharmaceutical Export Promotion Council of India (Pharmexcil), will lead a business delegation to four ASEAN nations, Myanmar, Cambodia, Malaysia, and Vietnam, in March 2026. The delegation aims to boost and foster Indian pharmaceutical exports in ASEAN markets, thereby further integrating India and ASEAN and widening the partnership (Maritime Gateway, 2026). India-ASEAN socio-cultural cooperation functions as a normative pillar, binding them together with the aim of holistic development and long-term stability of the region.

4.2 Economic and Connectivity Imperatives

The year 2022 marked thirty years of relationship between India and ASEAN, when India launched its Look East Policy (LEP) in 1992 under the prime ministerialship of PV Narsimha Rao, leading to the establishment of a sectoral dialogue partnership between the two. The year 1996 marked the conversion from being sectoral dialogue partners to full-fledged dialogue partners. In 2002, India and ASEAN enhanced their relationship at the summit level, with India also becoming a dialogue partner of the East Asia Summit and participating in the first summit held in December 2005 at Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. The year 2009 marked the signing of the ASEAN-India Trade in Goods Agreement (AITGA) (implemented in 2010) in goods, followed by the ASEAN-India Trade in Services Agreement in 2014. India also elevated its Look East Policy to the Act East Policy (AEP) under PM Modi, emphasising a more proactive and action-oriented approach in East Asia, Southeast Asia and Oceania. AEP extended the

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geographical scope of India’s orientation and focused on culture, commerce, connectivity, and capacity building, or what can be referred as the 4Cs (Devi, 2025).

Economy is one of the most important pillars between two nations that binds them together, and in this regard, India and ASEAN share strong convergence. Due to geographical proximity, shared cultural and historical ties, and converging interests and understanding, trade ties between India and ASEAN are a strong point, as evidenced in Table 1. In the 2024 fiscal year, India-ASEAN trade was valued at USD120 billion, showcasing the deeply intertwined trade ties between them, and the bloc is one of the top five trading partners of India, alongside the US, China, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), and the European Union (EU) (Singh, 2025).

Table 1: Bilateral Trade Statistics (USD Billion)

India’s trade with ASEAN	Export	Import	Total	Trade Balance
2016-17	30.961	40.617	71.578	-9.656
2017-18	34.203	47.133	81.336	-12.93
2018-19	37.473	59.321	96.794	-21.848
2019-20	31.546	55.369	86.915	-23.823
2020-21	31.485	47.420	78.90	-15.93
2021-22	42.327	68.07	110.39	-25.75
2022-23	44.00	87.58	131.58	-43.58
2023-24	41.21	79.66	120.89	-38.45
2024-25	(Up to Feb 2025) 35.87	77.09	112.97	-41.20

Source: Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India.

Table 1, while showcasing the booming India-ASEAN trade, also highlights a concerning trend, i.e., increasing trade balance and trade deficit. These deeper asymmetries between India and the bloc reveal that India opened its market far more than ASEAN did, leading to greater imports and lesser exports of India vis-à-vis ASEAN. Since the functionality of AITGA, India’s exports have fallen from 10.2 percent to 8.9 percent, while its share in imports increased from 8.3 percent to 11.7 percent. India is now moving towards an approach to ensure symmetry so that gains are not one-sided, resolve non-tariff barriers effectively, tighten rules of origin and create fast dispute resolution mechanisms (Roy, 2025).

Beyond trade, connectivity and infrastructure projects between the two are also emerging rapidly. The India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway is one of the flagship projects connecting these three nations via land, serving as a cornerstone to India’s Act East Policy. Although physical connectivity between India and Southeast Asia is facing challenges, such as inadequate infrastructure, bureaucratic delays, and geopolitical constraints, initiatives such as the India–Myanmar–Thailand Trilateral Highway and the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project still seek to address these obstacles. While both projects have encountered implementation challenges, they remain critical in enhancing overland and maritime connectivity between Northeast India and Southeast Asia. Moreover, Japan and the Asian Development Bank (ADB) have played supportive roles in India’s Northeast infrastructure development, aiming to foster greater regional integration (Ministry of Finance, 2023). Table 2 enlists the infrastructure and connectivity projects between India and ASEAN, synergising their strategic ties.

Table 2: Infrastructure and Connectivity projects between India and ASEAN

S.N.	Project	Short Description	Status
1	India–Myanmar–Thailand (IMT) Trilateral Highway (2002)	1,360 km transnational land corridor intended to connect Moreh (Manipur, India) → Tamu/Kalewa (Myanmar) → Mae Sot (Thailand).	At least 30 percent of total construction remains in various stages of completion owing to the security situation in Myanmar (Padmanabhan & Krishnankutty, 2024).
2	Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project (KMMTTP / Kaladan) (2008)	International Transport Project envisaged under four stages: 1. Kolkata to Sittwe waterway 2. Sittwe to Paletwa inland (River Kaladan) waterway 3. Paletwa to India-Myanmar border post in Myanmar	According to Union Minister of Ports, Shipping & Waterways Sarbananda Sonowal, the project will be fully operational by 2027 (Singh, 2025).

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		4. Linking the road to Lawngtlai in Mizoram as part of the project's last leg	
3	Sabang (Aceh) port cooperation (India-Indonesia) (2018)	Joint feasibility and cooperation for developing Sabang deep-sea port (Aceh, Indonesia) to enhance short-sea links to Andaman & Nicobar / Malacca approaches; strategically important for wider India-ASEAN maritime connectivity and India's larger Indo-Pacific vision.	A joint feasibility study was completed (reported May 2023); discussions/feasibility are ongoing for development and cooperation (Mattoo, 2023).

(1) India-Myanmar-Thailand (IMT) Trilateral Highway (2002)

The IMT Trilateral Highway was envisioned in 2002, with its construction beginning only in 2012. The project was aimed to be completed by 2015, failing which 2020 was set as the revised year of completion. At present, the project still remains incomplete. A major reason for this delay is the political turmoil ongoing in Myanmar, where a civil war-like situation is going on between the National Unity Government (and its armed wing, the People's Defence Force) and the military junta (NDTV, 2025). Other reasons for the delay include bureaucratic hurdles, lack of a comprehensive India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Motor Vehicles Agreement (IMT-TMVA), differing national regulations on permits, customs, and security checks, issues relating to the terrain and the environment, ethnic conflicts and insurgency in India's Northeast, and the COVID-19 pandemic (Chatterjee, 2025). Around 70 percent of the work had been completed by July 2023, and during the 12th meeting of the Mekong Ganga Cooperation (MGC) initiative in July 2023, Jaishankar reiterated the speedy completion of the project. At the 7th Indian Ocean Conference in 2024, Jaishankar also affirmed the significance of connectivity across the Indian Ocean Region (IOR), and the IMT Trilateral Highway to India's east will complement the India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) to India's west (Padmanabhan & Krishnankutty, 2024). Figure 2 gives a clear picture of the connectivity from India's Moreh to Thailand's Mae Sot, with Myanmar lying in between the two.

Figure 2: Map of India-Myanmar-Thailand (IMT) Trilateral Highway

Source: ASEAN-India Development and Cooperation Report: Avenues for Cooperation in Indo-Pacific, p. 196.

(2) Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project (KMMTTP / Kaladan) (2008)

The Kaladan Multi-Modal Transport Project is an attempt by India to enhance strong connectivity ties between the Indian mainland and the Northeast region. At present, both these regions are connected by a narrow 22-kilometre-wide Siliguri Corridor, or Chicken Neck, lying in the Siliguri district of West Bengal. This corridor holds immense strategic importance, as any disturbance in this stretch will cut off the northeast region from mainland India. China creates problems for India time and again, as it aims to

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contain the Siliguri Corridor. The Doklam standoff in 2017 was an attempt by China to get closer to the Siliguri Corridor to maintain its strategic presence.

Given the geographical proximity between India and Bangladesh, the latter is set to be India's viable and easy option to connect mainland India with India's northeast. But India-Bangladesh relations have always been subject to the political leadership in Bangladesh. Sheikh Hasina, with whom India's relations have always been good, was ousted in August 2024, following huge protests in the country over the quota system, with 30 percent reservation given to the children and grandchildren of the freedom fighters of the Bangladesh Liberation Movement. Following this, Muhammad Yunus was given a mandate to form an interim government in August 2024; at present, he serves as the chief advisor of the interim government (elections in Bangladesh are expected to be held by 2026). Yunus has been a critic of India (and pro-China) and brought to notice the "landlocked northeast" during his visit to China (Mukul 2025).

With the current political situation in Bangladesh, India was prompted to bypass Bangladesh by operationalising the connectivity of 540 km between Kolkata Port and Sittwe Port (Myanmar) via sea. Sittwe Port will be connected to Paletwa via the Kaladan River, covering a distance of 158 km, and will finally be connected to Mizoram with a distance of 62 km (Deccan Herald Web Desk, 2025). The connectivity project will link the northeast region with the rest of the states, which will eventually lead to its development and progress (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Map of Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project

Source: De, Prabir. "Operationalisation of Sittwe Port and What It Means for Regional Connectivity in Bay of Bengal." Research and Information System for Developing Countries, May, 2023.

(3) Sabang (Aceh) port cooperation (India-Indonesia)

As part of the India-Indonesia Shared Vision on Maritime Cooperation in the Indo-Pacific, India and Indonesia are undergoing joint collaboration on the Sabang Port of Indonesia, with the aim to develop its port infrastructure. Lying at a distance of 500 km from the Strait of Malacca and 376 nautical miles from Port Blair, the port holds immense strategic importance for India in light of the growing presence and assertiveness of China in the Indo-Pacific (Bhaumik, 2024). The Malacca Strait is considered the most important chokepoint in the world, as it serves as the shortest route between the Indian Ocean and the Pacific Ocean, facilitating the movement of around 82,000 vessels annually (Rakha, 2025). Once the port is operationalised, it will complement the INS Baaz naval air station in the Andaman and Nicobar Islands, the southernmost air station of the Indian armed forces.

Sabang Port matters greatly for both India and Indonesia (Figure 4). With China's increasing presence in the region, the port provides an opportunity for India to keep an eye on the ongoing naval activities in the region. It also provides an opportunity for India to counterbalance China's increasing port diplomacy and presence in Hambantota, Gwadar, and Kyaukpyu, thereby enhancing India as a developmental partner in Southeast Asia. For Indonesia, the port enhances the country's maritime role in the Indo-Pacific as well as diversifies its partnership amid China's growing expansionism.

Figure 4: Sabang (Aceh) port cooperation (India–Indonesia)
Source: Indo-Pacific Defense Forum.

4.3 Maritime Governance and Security Cooperation

India and Southeast Asia share a strong convergence on the aspect of maritime governance and security cooperation in the Indo-Pacific. With the emerging contemporary maritime threats in the region, India and ASEAN have come together on the protection of SLOCs and adherence to the UNCLOS for a free, open, inclusive and rules-based regional order. India's support for UNCLOS can be exemplified by the 2016 PCA ruling in the Philippines v. China, wherein the court ruled in favour of the Philippines with regard to China's expansionist claims, including its nine-dash line, land reclamation activities, and other activities in Philippine waters. China declared the ruling as null and void and held that the United Nations (UN) does not hold any position on the case or on disputed claims (Campbell & Salidjanova, 2016). The sheer dismissal of the arbitration ruling constituted a direct challenge to the liberal institutional order. With respect to this case, India's Ministry of External Affairs (MEA) stated it had "noted the Award" and "reiterates the importance of freedom of navigation, overflight and unimpeded commerce, as reflected notably in UNCLOS" (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2016). This framed India's interest as rule-of-law, not claimant-specific.

India and the Philippines conducted their first joint sail and naval drill in the South China Sea on 3-4 August 2025, involving INS Delhi, INS Kiltan, and INS Shakti, alongside the Philippines, which deployed two frigates, BRP Miguel Malvar and BRP Jose Rizal, demonstrating India's legal position transcending into reality and interoperability (Aljazeera, 2025). China protested, reviving its "third-party interference" line (Gomez, 2025). Pressed on the exercise, MEA Secretary (East) P. Kumaran publicly restated India's doctrine:

We support freedom of navigation and legitimate commerce through the waters of the South China Sea. India has an abiding interest in peace and stability in the region. Our position is based on the UNCLOS. India also believes that any differences between the parties concerned should be resolved peacefully, without resorting to threat or force (The Telegraph, 2025).

Hence, this ties Indian activity directly to the UNCLOS rather than the bloc politics.

The ASEAN-India Plan of Action (2021–2025) was conceptualised in 2021 at the 18th ASEAN-India Summit, with the aim of greater cooperation in the domains of maritime security, counterterrorism and trade. Both India and ASEAN will work together on converging areas of interest in order to establish a rules-based order in the Indo-Pacific (Singh, 2021). The Plan of Action was reviewed at the 25th ASEAN-India Joint Cooperation Committee Meeting in February 2025, wherein ASEAN highlighted India's committed support towards fostering a meaningful Comprehensive Strategic Partnership (CSP) by enhancing India-ASEAN cooperation in maritime security, infrastructure development, funding modalities, and much more (ASEAN, 2025).

India and ASEAN are also part of various security frameworks in the Indo-Pacific (see table 3), as they share a common goal of making the maritime waters a peaceful arena, where all the nations abide by the rule of law as enshrined in the UNCLOS, and establishing a free, fair, open, inclusive and resilient Indo-Pacific. Being part of various forums, frameworks, and groupings enables India and ASEAN to work towards common goals in a nuanced manner.

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Table 3: Maritime Security Frameworks Involving India and ASEAN in the Indo-Pacific

Framework / Mechanism	Year Established	Main Maritime Focus
ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF)	1994	Confidence-building, maritime security dialogue, preventive diplomacy (ASEAN Regional Forum, n.d.).
East Asia Summit (EAS)	2005	Strategic and maritime cooperation; peace and security; freedom of navigation (East Asia Summit, n.d.).
Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA)	1997	Maritime safety and security, disaster risk management, fisheries management (Indian Ocean Rim Association, n.d.).
Indian Ocean Naval Symposium (IONS)	2008	Naval cooperation, information sharing among Indian Ocean Region (IOR) littorals (Indian Ocean Naval Symposium, n.d.).
ASEAN Defence Ministers' Meeting Plus (ADMM-Plus)	2010	Maritime security, joint exercises, defence cooperation, capacity-building (ASEAN Defence Ministers' Meeting, n.d.).
Regional Cooperation Agreement on Combating Piracy and Armed Robbery against Ships in Asia (ReCAAP)	2006	Anti-piracy, Information Sharing Centre (ISC) established in Singapore for the exchange of regional security information and operational responses, thereby enhancing maritime domain awareness (MDA) in tackling the issue of piracy and reducing crimes (ReCAAP, n.d.).

Source: Compiled by the authors using cited sources in the table

The table above presents an overview of the main elements of India–ASEAN security cooperation, highlighting progress made through sustained institutional engagement but also conveying its changing strategic importance. This trajectory has been consolidated with India’s Act East Policy and resonated in the development of a converging Indo-Pacific outlook since 2021. The recent launch of initiatives such as the first-ever ASEAN–India Maritime Exercise (AIME-2023) indicates a transition from declaratory intent to enhanced operational synchronisation. Yet the success of such initiatives will ultimately hinge on their continuity, scalability and institutionalisation. Within this framework, designating 2026 as the “ASEAN–India Maritime Cooperation Year” is an important opportunity to translate intent into outcomes and to make real progress in areas such as humanitarian assistance and disaster relief (HADR), the blue economy, and maritime security.

5. CONCLUSION

India and ASEAN are traditional partners with shared history and culture. The strategic relations between them have progressively evolved in response to the shifting strategic dynamics in the Indo-Pacific. The increasing importance of maritime security challenges and intensifying geopolitical competitions have reinforced the need for a deeper and more institutionalised India-ASEAN engagement aimed at sustaining a rule-based order. The elevation of ties to a comprehensive strategic partnership at the 22nd ASEAN Summit (2025), alongside initiatives for sustainable development, renewable energy cooperation, and knowledge exchange, reflects a broadening and diversifying partnership between the two. However, the realisation of its full potential remains contingent upon addressing persistent structural and institutional constraints. Trade imbalances, along with delays in infrastructure projects and connectivity, and bureaucratic inefficiencies, continue to hinder progress. Furthermore, regional multilateral frameworks such as the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF), East Asia Summit (EAS), Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA), and Indian Ocean Naval Symposium (IONS), while valuable for dialogue, are limited by weak institutional capacity, consensus-driven decision-making, and inadequate enforcement mechanisms. To move beyond a primarily consultative framework, India and ASEAN must prioritise a shift towards outcome-oriented cooperation through institutional strengthening, streamlined implementation mechanisms, and enhanced financial and political commitment. Consequently, a more balanced economic partnership, improved project execution, and strengthened regional institutions will be critical to advancing shared visions and goals. Ultimately, enduring synergies and convergence between India and ASEAN hold significant potential to foster stability, resilience, and an inclusive, rules-based order in the Indo-Pacific.

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